

Prioritizing biomarkers as objective measures of nutrient and food intake for dietary surveys

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Table of Contents

1. Background	3
2. Methods.....	4
3. Biological Samples	5
Urinary biomarkers.....	5
Blood samples biomarkers.....	6
4. Biomarkers of Intake.....	7
4.1 Biomarkers of Nutrient Intake.....	12
Protein	12
Fatty acids	13
Sugar.....	14
Sodium	14
Potassium.....	16
4.2 Biomarkers of Food Intake	16
Dairy products and dairy fat.....	17
Fish.....	18
Fruits and vegetables	19
Whole-grain wheat and rye.....	21
5. Conclusions.....	23
6. Funding	24
7. References	24
Supplementary Material.....	31

1. Background

Dietary surveys are an essential tool for understanding the nutritional status and dietary habits of populations. Nevertheless, achieving accurate and reliable dietary assessments in surveys can be hindered by various factors. Among the challenges, a prominent issue is the occurrence of misreporting when individuals self-report their diets using methods like 24-hour dietary recalls or food frequency questionnaires. The misreporting arises from individuals struggling to remember the specific foods they consumed or to provide precise estimates of the amounts ingested. As a result, underreporting of certain foods or nutrients can occur, while others may be over-reported (1). Respondents may also provide answers they think are more socially acceptable or desirable, leading to the over-reporting of healthy foods and under-reporting of unhealthy foods (2). Estimating portion sizes can also be difficult, as individuals may not be familiar with standard serving sizes or have different methods of estimating portion sizes (3). Another challenge is the limited availability of complete and accurate food composition databases. This can result in missing or inaccurate estimates of nutrient intake (1).

Biomarkers of intake are chemical compounds that are measured in biological samples and are used to provide an objective assessment of dietary intake (1). Several biomarkers have been validated in controlled feeding studies and have demonstrated good reproducibility, sensitivity, and specificity (4). Biomarkers of intake have several advantages over self-reported dietary assessment methods, including that they are not prone to misreporting errors. Biomarkers of intake may provide a more accurate measure of dietary intake and can therefore be used to validate other dietary assessment methods (4, 5). Furthermore, biomarkers of intake can be used directly to estimate the intake of specific nutrients or food components in a population at a certain point or over time (1, 4). They can be used to rank individuals according to intake and to develop calibration equations to correct other dietary data. Thus, the measurement of biomarkers of intake is a valuable complementary approach to standard self-report assessment tools in dietary surveys.

Although there is a lack of valid markers for many specific food components or nutrients, a few biomarkers of intake are well-established (1, 4). However, some limitations exist, such as variability in individual metabolism affecting biomarker levels, differences in absorption and excretion rates, and the timeframe of intake reflected (5). Also, requirements and participant burden for biological sample collection or costs for laboratory measurements may represent barriers to the application of biomarkers in surveys.

The purpose of this review was to summarize the most established and promising biomarkers of intake to consider in dietary surveys. Based on an exploratory literature review, we provided an overview of their advantages and limitations, considering the validity, reliability and specificity, the sample collection and participant burden. Moreover, we summarized the primary biological matrices used for biomarker measurements and presented some of their advantages and limitations.

2. Methods

An exploratory review was conducted to identify relevant literature. The identification of candidate biomarkers was based on screening books, databases/toolkits, and scientific publications. The search was initially conducted in two books: "Principles of Nutritional Assessment"(1) and "Nutritional Epidemiology"(4) as well as dietary assessment toolkits extracted from a review (6). The toolkits that included biomarkers were: "Diet, Anthropometry and Physical Activity Measurement Toolkit (DAPA; UK)" (7) and the National Cancer Institute's (NCI) Dietary Assessment Primer (USA) (8) (**Supplementary Table 1**).

To be included in this report, the biomarker should reflect either nutrients, food components, or food groups. The inclusion of biomarkers was based on the frequency of reporting and how the different information sources reported their validity. Biomarkers of energy intake, vitamins, and minerals were outside of the scope of this report. However, urinary potassium and sodium have been included because they are well-established biomarkers of dietary intake and have been used frequently to assess absolute intake (1, 4).

While circulating folate was mentioned by three of the four sources, it was not included because it is a less sensitive biomarker of fruits and vegetables than vitamin C and carotenoids, and it lacks specificity considering many other foods are sources of folate (4). Similarly, polyphenols were also not included because they are not good biomarkers for fruits and vegetables as a whole group, as they are only present in selected fruit and vegetables (4).

Certain biomarkers were mentioned exclusively in either one of the sources. Besides the infrequent reporting in our source publications, there are further reasons for exclusion from the current review. Cholesterol was not included in this review due to its other determinants not directly linked to intake, such as endogenous synthesis (4). Proline betaine, a promising biomarker of citrus fruit (1), was also not included in this review due to limited evidence regarding its sensitivity and specificity with the intake of different citrus foods. Also, this biomarker is unlikely to be a marker for fruits and vegetables as a whole group. Similarly, 1-methyl-histidine and 3-methyl-histidine, proposed biomarkers of meat consumption (1), were not included due to the need for further studies to validate their effectiveness (9).

A reference screening was also used to identify relevant literature for this review, whereby references cited in the initial sources were used to identify more studies. Data were summarized from the selected sources using a data extraction form, included as a main table. The form included information such as dietary components measured, biomarker, biological sample, validity, reproducibility, limitations. A literature search was carried out to obtain the necessary information for details that were missing in the initial sources.

3. Biological Samples

Dietary biomarkers can be measured in various biological matrices, including blood, adipose tissue, urine, feces, hair, and nails. The choice of the matrix depends on the type of biomarker, the nutrient or compound of interest, and the timeframe over which the intake is being assessed (4). For example, blood and urine samples are commonly used to measure short-term nutrient intake, while hair and nail samples are often used to assess long-term nutrient intake. Fecal samples may be used to measure the intake of nutrients or compounds that are not well-absorbed by the body and excreted in the feces (4).

Although biomarkers like fatty acids can be measured in adipose tissue as well (1), the selected biomarkers of intake (**Supplementary Table 1**) are principally measured in urine and blood fractions and will be, therefore, summarized in the following paragraphs.

Urinary biomarkers

Collecting urine is practical and feasible to identify biomarkers since many metabolic byproducts are excreted in the urine (5). Urine biomarkers are determined in spot urine samples or, preferably, in samples collected over 24 hours (1, 10). Biomarkers collected in urine have many advantages. Urine sampling is non-invasive, generally inexpensive, and allows the collection of large volumes (4, 10).

Another advantage is that some urinary biomarkers have a direct relationship between absolute intake and urine excretion. For example, 24-hour urinary nitrogen, sodium, and potassium reflect recent dietary intake (1). To obtain a reliable measurement of long-term exposure, multiple 24-hour urine samples collected over time are necessary (11).

The urine collection for 24 hours provides a broader picture compared to a single spot collection (4, 11). The process involves collecting all urine produced for 24 hours in a specialized container. During this time, the individual must store the container in a cool place and ensure all urine is collected and accounted for (12). While collecting urine is not difficult, it can be inconvenient and time-consuming, and some people may find it uncomfortable and logistically difficult, which may affect response rates.

Considering that 24-hour urine collection can be burdensome for some participants, the risk of incomplete samples is a concern. When 24-hour urine samples are used, para-aminobenzoic acid (PABA) can be used to assess the completeness of the urine collection (1, 4). Participants should take three tablets throughout the day, and PABA is excreted in the urine. Some limitations include declining PABA excretion with higher age, non-adherence to the PABA dosage and timing (regime), and potential interactions with other medications (13). Moreover, it has been suggested that, instead of checking PABA completeness in all participants to exclude incomplete samples (<85% PABA), PABA could be used selectively only in participants with low levels of the biomarker or when incompleteness is suspected (14).

Another limitation is the sample variability. Urine biomarkers can be influenced by various factors, including diet, hydration levels, and medications, which can affect the accuracy of the results (4). Moreover, handling and processing urine samples can affect the accuracy and reliability of the results (4).

Blood samples biomarkers

Blood contains a wide range of biomarkers that can be used to assess nutrient intake, including vitamins, minerals, and fatty acids. Measuring these biomarkers reflects the absorption and transport of these nutrients. Circulating biomarkers can detect the intake of specific nutrients that may be difficult to assess accurately through dietary questionnaires, such as certain fatty acids in very low concentration.

Depending on which fraction is analysed, circulating biomarkers may reflect the acute or long-term intake of certain nutrients (1). Serum and plasma are the most common fractions (4), although red blood cells (erythrocytes) are also widely used.

Blood samples are minimally invasive. The participant burden of the sample collection varies depending on the circumstances. Having blood drawn may be uncomfortable or cause anxiety for some individuals, while others may experience little to no discomfort. There may also be eating or drinking restrictions before the blood draw, depending on the specific biomarkers being tested (1). Collecting fasting blood samples reduces the potential effect of recent dietary intake on blood concentrations.

Circulating biomarkers have some limitations. There is a need for a trained professional to collect and handle the blood samples. Some biomarker testing may be costly and time-consuming, limiting their widespread use in large population surveys. Numerous factors, including fasting status, previous meal consumption, diurnal variations, hydration levels, medications, infections, inflammation, stress, body weight, and genotype, may confound the interpretation of the results (1).

4. Biomarkers of Intake

Although various concepts regarding the validation of biomarkers exist, universally accepted validation criteria for dietary intake biomarkers are currently lacking. However, significant progress has been made in the development of criteria for validating food intake biomarkers, encompassing aspects such as plausibility, dose–response, time–response, robustness, reliability, stability, analytical performance, and reproducibility (15).

Biomarkers of intake that are suitable for monitoring dietary exposure in surveys and epidemiological studies are limited to a small number of specific nutrients and foods (16). These biomarkers are characterized by their validity, reproducibility, sensitivity, and successful testing in both free-living and controlled intervention studies.

Biomarkers selected from the original sources screened are summarized in the next section and the summary table (**Table 1**) in the following order: biomarkers of nutrient intake (protein, fatty acids, sugar, sodium, potassium) and biomarkers of food intake (dairy fat, fish, fruits and vegetables, and whole-grain wheat and rye).

Noteworthy, intake biomarkers can be classified into recovery biomarkers, concentration biomarkers and predictive biomarkers. Recovery biomarkers are directly associated with actual intake. They can be used to determine absolute intake and can be used as reference to evaluate and rectify inaccuracies in self-reported dietary information. Recovery biomarkers are urinary nitrogen as a biomarker of protein intake, urinary potassium, and urinary sodium. Concentration biomarkers correlate with dietary intake, but are not suitable for determining absolute intake due to their higher susceptibility to metabolic processes and individual characteristics. Concentration biomarkers are fatty acids as biomarkers of their intake from different sources (e.g., vegetable oils, nuts, seeds, dairy fat, fish), and biomarkers for fruits and vegetables (plasma vitamin C and plasma carotenoids). Predictive biomarkers are between concentration biomarkers and recovery biomarkers. They exhibit a significantly stronger association with intake compared to concentration biomarkers and are responsive to intake in a dose-dependent way, but the recovery of the intake amount is insufficient to classify them as recovery biomarkers (17). Urinary sucrose and fructose for sugar intake is a predictive biomarker (7, 8).

Table 1. Summary of biomarkers of intake of food components and food groups

Dietary component measured	Biomarker	Biological sample	Validity	Reproducibility	Limitations	Other notes
Protein	Nitrogen	24-hour urine	~83.5 % of dietary intake of nitrogen in the form of protein is recovered in urine (18) The correlations coefficients (r) between nitrogen intake and urinary nitrogen were high (r = 0.99 (19); r = 0.92 (20))	Good reproducibility Intra-class correlation (ICC) = 0.59 (20), 0.47 (21), 0.60 (22), and 0.73 (22)	It depends on the assumption that subjects are in a stable nitrogen balance Variability: renal function, extrarenal loss, hydration status, and urine volume	It can be used to calculate absolute protein intake. The exact number of urinary collections depends on the degree of precision required (23).
Fatty acids	- n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA): Linoleic acid (LA) -n-3 PUFAs: α -linolenic acid (ALA), docosahexanoic acid (DHA) and eicosapentanoic acid (EPA) - Trans fatty acids (TFA) - Odd chain fatty acids (OCFA)	Adipose tissue and blood fractions	These fatty acids that are not synthesized endogenously correlate well with dietary intake.	Fair to good reproducibility: ICC = 0.60 for ALA, 0.59 for LA, 0.72 total TFA (24) (OCFA, DHA, and EPA are presented below)	Competition between metabolic pathways may lead to changes in fatty acid composition not directly related to diet (25). Variability: genetics, smoking, obesity, sex, physical activity, recent meal composition, and the use of supplements Changes in the percentage of one fatty acid can influence the distribution of others.	The choice of biological sample depends on the time frame of interest. Careful sample analysis is required to analyse the very low concentrations of TFA, OCFA and n-3 PUFAs.
Sugar	Sucrose and fructose sum	24-hour urine	Dose-response relation with intake Strong correlation with intake in controlled	Fair to good reproducibility: ICC = 0.67 (17) and 0.41 (27)	Variability: absorption, tissue uptake, excretion, medications, stress, illness, and dietary and lifestyle factors (28)	It was significantly correlated with added sugar intake but not with natural sugar (in

Dietary component measured	Biomarker	Biological sample	Validity	Reproducibility	Limitations	Other notes
			feeding studies with all food provided (r = 0.84 (26), r = 0.88) (17)		It is not suitable for people with diabetes or kidney disease	fruits and vegetables) (26).
Sodium/Salt intake	Sodium	24-hour urine	90-95% of sodium intake is excreted in urine	Low to moderate reproducibility: ICC = 0.46 (29), 0.32-55 (11)	Variability: seasonal (10%) (4), stool excretion, sweat excretion, hydration status, health status, hormonal changes It may not be suitable for individuals with renal impairments	Two or three 24-hour urine collections are required if the aim of the survey is to estimate the distribution of sodium intake in adults A single urine collection is sufficient if the aim of the survey is to obtain the population mean
Potassium	Potassium	24-hour urine	77% of dietary potassium is excreted in urine (4, 30) High correlations of 24-hour urinary potassium with measured intake (r = 0.89) (20) and estimated intake (4)	Moderate reproducibility: ICC of 0.50 (n=13) (20) and 48-65 (11)	Variability: fiber intake, hydration status, medication use It may not be suitable for individuals with renal impairments	Suitable to estimate absolute intake (31) Two 24-hour samples were sufficient for measuring long-term potassium exposure (11).
Dairy Fat	OCFA: pentadecanoic acid (15:0) and heptadecanoic acid (17:0)	Adipose tissue, and blood fractions	15:0 concentration is more strongly correlated with dietary intake than 17:0 (32, 33)	Good reproducibility for 15:0 (ICC = 0.72) and moderate for 17:0 (ICC = 0.52) (24).	17:0 concentrations may be influenced by endogenous biosynthesis OCFA are not completely specific to dairy intake and can also be found in small concentrations in other animal products, such as marine fish (34)	The correlations of dairy fat intake and 15:0 were higher in adipose tissue (33), but it is debatable which blood fraction best reflects dietary intake.

Dietary component measured	Biomarker	Biological sample	Validity	Reproducibility	Limitations	Other notes
Marine fish and fish oil	DHA (22:6n-3) Sum of EPA (20:5n-3) and DHA	Adipose tissue / Blood fractions	EPA+DHA concentrations increase in a dose-response manner after fish intake (35) High specificity to shellfish and fish (in particular, fatty fish such as salmon, tuna, herring, and mackerel)	Good reproducibility ICC = 0.68 for EPA and 0.73 for DHA (24).	Variability: type of fish, supplements use, genetic influences in metabolism Most studies evaluating these biomarkers used fish oil instead of fish intake (9) Eggs and meats from livestock fed with diets high in n-3 may also provide some quantities of EPA and DHA, but marine and freshwater foods represent by far the main dietary source of n-3. Humans can also synthesize EPA and DHA by converting α -linolenic acid (ALA), but the conversion rate of ALA derived from plant sources is low.	The choice of tissue for measuring n-3 fatty acids depends on the duration of consumption under investigation. Shorter-term intake can be reflected in plasma and serum, while red blood cell membranes and adipose tissue are more indicative of long-term (habitual) fish consumption (25, 36, 37).
Fruit and vegetables	Carotenoids	Plasma	Some evidence suggests dose-response relation with intake (38, 39)* The sum of carotenoids other than lycopene may be more strongly correlated with total fruit and vegetable than the sum including lycopene (4).	Good reproducibility: ICC = 0.81 (24), 0.70 (40), and 0.81 (41)	Variability: energy intake, alcohol intake, plasma lipids concentrations, BMI, genetics, and smoking (30) Factors that affect bioavailability: - Ingestion with other foods (higher fat intake increasing their bioavailability (42), while fiber intake may decrease it (43)) - Heat (cooking) and mechanical treatment (chopping, homogenization) It is not useful for people with abnormal lipid metabolism or liver dysfunction	Marker of carotenoid-rich foods (30) *The evidence for a dose-response relationship is still limited.
	Vitamin C	Plasma or serum	Concentrations increase after higher intakes of fruits and vegetables in comparison with lower intakes (44), (45).	Large variation in reproducibility: ICC = 0.29 (41) and 0.84 (40)	Variability: smoking, inflammation, BMI, and food preparation (46) Sensitivity to short-term intake (3h) (4)	Not enough evidence to support the dose-response relation

Dietary component measured	Biomarker	Biological sample	Validity	Reproducibility	Limitations	Other notes
					<p>It has been suggested that the response may follow a linear trend only at lower intakes (47).</p> <p>Cooking vegetables and prolonged storage of fruits and vegetables can lead to declining vitamin C levels.</p>	
Whole-Grain Wheat/Rye	Alkylresorcinol (AR)	Plasma, red blood cells (RBC)	Plasma AR was correlated with intake estimated by weighted food records ($r = 0.58$ (48) and $r = 0.53$ (49)).	Moderate to high reproducibility: ICC = 0.88-0.90 (50) and 0.47 (49)	Because of their brief half-life (approximately 5 hours), these biomarkers primarily indicate short-term intake, unless whole-grain wheat and/or rye consumption occurs consistently (more than twice daily).	Alkylresorcinols can also be measured in 24-hour urine samples.

4.1 Biomarkers of Nutrient Intake

Protein

Nitrogen measured in 24-hour urine samples reflects the intake of protein, a vital component for the growth, development, and maintenance of body tissues. This biomarker assumes a stable nitrogen balance, where there is neither nitrogen retention from muscle growth or repair nor nitrogen loss caused by starvation, dieting, or injury (23). In this scenario, the nitrogen intake would be directly associated with nitrogen excretion. The correlations between nitrogen intake and urinary nitrogen are high, as has been shown in controlled metabolic ward studies with repeated assessments of nitrogen intake and urinary nitrogen ($r = 0.99$ (19) and $r = 0.92$ (20)).

Nitrogen in diet, urine, feces, and skin was measured in the participants living during 28 days in a metabolic unit, where duplicates of all food eaten were taken for nitrogen measurement. It was defined that urine nitrogen was 81% of dietary nitrogen (19). Similar results were later available from a meta-analysis of controlled feeding studies which estimated that 83.5 % of dietary nitrogen intake in protein is recovered in urine (18).

Urinary nitrogen can be used to estimate absolute protein intakes. The extrarenal nitrogen loss via skin and feces could be accounted for by adding 2 grams of nitrogen to the urinary measurement (51) or accounting for a fixed proportion (23). For example, the urinary nitrogen (in grams) is divided by 0.81 to convert to dietary nitrogen grams and then multiplied by 6.25 to get the dietary protein intake (22, 52).

Within-subject variation in nitrogen excretion may be large and multiple collections of urine samples are beneficial. The exact number of samples depends on the degree of precision required (19). In a study with 8 participants in a metabolic unit for 28 days, the average daily coefficient of variation (CV) was 13% for urinary nitrogen (19). In a similar strictly controlled study with urinary collections for 30 days ($n = 13$), the within-person CV was 14.5%, and the intra-class correlation (ICC) was 0.59 (20).

Other studies have reported similar reliability of urinary nitrogen with two samples. The ICC between 24-hour urine samples approximately two weeks apart was 0.47 in the INTERSALT study ($n = 805$) (21) and was 0.60 in the Observing Protein and Energy Nutrition (OPEN) study ($n = 297$) (22). In the Automated Multiple-Pass Method (AMPM) study ($n = 51$), with two samples 16 months apart, the ICC was 0.73 (22). Furthermore, Pearson correlations between repeated urinary nitrogen taken twice six months apart were 0.46 in the Women's Health Initiative (WHI) ($n = 111$) (53). When six 24-hour urinary samples were collected over nine months, their correlation (average over repeated measures) was 0.58 in the European Prospective Investigation into Cancer (EPIC)-Norfolk ($n = 123$) (54).

Because previous feeding studies using urinary nitrogen found no appreciable bias in this biomarker, 24-hour urine nitrogen is commonly used for validating other dietary assessments (23). For example, 24-hour urinary nitrogen is widely used to validate self-reported dietary intake from food frequency questionnaires or 24-hour recalls

(55). Additionally, this biomarker serves as a valuable tool for comparing the performance of different dietary assessment methods (56). Moreover, to enhance the accuracy of data collected by self-report tools, calibration equations and deattenuation factors can be employed.

Fatty acids

Intake of specific fatty acids is usually measured with biomarkers by measuring fatty acids in blood fractions or adipose tissue (1). Dietary fat is broken down into individual fatty acids, which are then transported in the bloodstream and deposited in adipose tissue. The concentrations of certain fatty acids in tissues can reflect an individual's dietary fat intake, particularly those not synthesized endogenously. Commonly used biomarkers of fat intake are the omega-3 fatty acids α -linolenic acid eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), the omega-6 linoleic acid, trans fatty acids and saturated odd chain fatty acids (OCFA) (25). EPA and DHA will be discussed in detail in the next section as biomarkers of fish intake, while OCFA will be discussed as markers of dairy fat intake.

These fatty acids are commonly measured in the tissues as a percentage of total measured fatty acids (4). The choice of tissue depends on the time frame of interest: adipose tissue reflects dietary intake over a more extended period than blood fractions (4, 25). Adipose tissue is assumed to reflect intake from the past 1-2 years, platelets reflect intake in the last few days, erythrocytes reflect intake in recent months, cholesteryl esters and phospholipids reflect intake in the past few days and weeks, and triglycerides reflect short term intake (past few hours or days) (25). Still, there is no consensus on which fraction best reflects intake.

The participant burden depends on which tissue is measured: if blood or adipose tissue samples are collected (25). Blood sampling was addressed in the previous section. The participant burden of adipose tissue biopsies can vary depending on the individual's pain tolerance, the methods used to extract the tissue, and the size and location of the biopsy site. Generally, adipose tissue biopsies are considered a low-risk and minimally invasive procedure, with most participants experiencing only mild discomfort or pain during the sampling procedure (25).

The reproducibility of repeated measurements of plasma fatty acids was fair to good when measured in the Nurses' Health Study ($n = 40$). The ICC based on two plasma samples over 1-2 years were 0.60 for α -linolenic acid, 0.59 for linoleic acid, and 0.72 for the sum of trans fatty acids (24).

Genetic variability, smoking, obesity, sex, physical activity, recent meal composition (total dietary fat, for example), and the use of supplements are factors that influence the reliability. Moreover, factors such as sample storage conditions, fasting status, and individual variations in lipid metabolism can affect the results. It is important to note that competition between metabolic pathways may lead to changes in fatty acid composition not directly related to dietary intake (25).

A crucial constraint when using fatty acids as biomarkers of intake is that, when expressed as percentages of total fatty acids, they offer relative rather than absolute measures of fatty acid intake. As a result, changes in one fatty acid can influence the

distribution of others, with the fatty acids present in lower percentages being particularly affected.

Overall, adipose tissue and circulating fatty acid composition are valuable markers of intake of a limited set of fatty acids and can be used to improve dietary assessments. When interpreting the results, it is essential to consider the limitations.

Sugar

The 24-hour urinary sucrose and fructose sum is used as a biomarker of added sugar intake (28). These urinary sugars, recovered in a very low proportion (~0.05% of intake), have a high correlation with the consumption of sugar (17). In a strictly controlled study, 24-hour urinary sugars (sucrose+fructose) were significantly correlated with extrinsic (added) sugar intake but not with intrinsic sugar (natural sugar in fruits and vegetables) (26). This biomarker shows a dose-response, time-dependent, and stable relationship with intake (8).

Despite having small sample sizes, the feeding studies from which this biomarker was derived were highly controlled (28). The dose-response relationship was evaluated in 12 male participants using a randomized cross-over design with three diets with different sugar levels for ten days each. Significant correlations were observed between both sugar/sucrose intake and the combined concentration of sucrose and fructose in urine ($r = 0.88$) (17). In another study, when providing 13 men and women with all their food for 30 days and collecting 24-hour urine samples every day, the mean urinary sugars (sucrose+fructose) were correlated with total sugar intake ($r = 0.84$) (26). The within-person CV was 37%, but because of the high between-person variation (CV = 67%), there was a high reproducibility (ICC = 0.67) (17). In an observational validation study with Dutch women and men ($n = 198$), the ICC of two 24-hour urine samples one year apart was 0.41 (27).

Bias may originate from between-person variation in absorption, tissue uptake, and excretion (28). Urinary sugar levels can be influenced by factors such as dietary or lifestyle factors, genetics, medications, and illness, which can affect accuracy (28). Also, this biomarker may not be suitable for individuals with certain health conditions that affect the metabolism or excretion of sugars, such as diabetes or kidney disease.

Still, urinary sugars can be used in large population-based studies to estimate sugar intake and to validate and calibrate self-reported intakes (57). For example, studies in the United Kingdom (17) and the United States (57, 58) have developed biomarker calibration equations to assess measurement errors in self-reported sugar intake. Additional highly-controlled studies in different populations to determine the performance and stability in large sample sizes are crucial.

Sodium

The 24-hour urinary sodium is considered a valid measure of sodium intake because it provides a comprehensive assessment of sodium intake over a full day, which is assumed to represent an individual's habitual intake (59). Sodium is a major component of salt and has been associated with an increased risk of hypertension and cardiovascular disease. For example, in a pooled analysis of six prospective

cohorts, a higher sodium intake, measured with at least two 24-hour urine collections, was associated with higher cardiovascular events risk in a dose–response manner (60).

It has been defined that around 90-95% of sodium intake is excreted in urine (4, 61). Sodium is also excreted via feces and sweat, and a seasonal variation of 10% has been suggested (4). The accuracy of the measurement depends on the completeness of the urine collection and factors including health status, hydration status, and hormonal changes (61). Noteworthy, a study controlling sodium intake for months revealed that cyclic sodium patterns independent of sodium intake could be longer than 24 hours (62).

Because urinary sodium has a very high within-person variation, this biomarker has a low reproducibility (4). The ICC was 0.46 in the INTERSALT Study (n = 807), with two 24-hour urine samples two weeks apart (29). In other studies, the ICC were 0.40-0.55 with two samples within a month (n = 2439) (11), while the ICC were 0.32-0.34 with four collections over one year (n = 742) (11). In studies using repeated urine samples, it was estimated that three collections of 24-hour urine are required to obtain a stable measurement of long-term sodium intake in adults (11) and children (63)

The World Health Organization (WHO), instead, indicates that a single 24-hour urine sample is sufficient for population surveys (59). They suggest that an accurate assessment of the population's average salt intake can be achieved by measuring 24-hour urinary sodium excretion in a representative sample, which helps estimate baseline population-level salt consumption and monitor trends and intervention effectiveness. The International Consortium for Quality Research on Dietary Sodium/Salt (TRUE) also advised that a single 24-hour urine sample from randomly selected individuals is sufficient to evaluate the current mean sodium intake within a population (64). One example among many surveys analysing sodium intake through 24-hour urine (65) is the survey conducted as part of the National Diet and Nutrition Survey (NDNS) to estimate salt intake in adults in England. This survey utilized single 24-hour urine samples (66). Still, it is clear that estimated distributions will be too wide when only a single urine collection is used. Therefore, optimally, repeated samples should be collected, unless an estimate of the ratio of within-person to the sum of the within- plus between-person variation from an external study with a comparable sample is available (7, 67).

Because the participant has to collect urine for 24 hours, which involves a considerable burden, some studies have investigated methods to estimate sodium intake with spot urine collections. However, the use of spot urine samples is not recommended by international health organizations (59). Some earlier research studies have found a consistent bias at the high and low ends of urinary sodium excretion when comparing estimates based on spot urine samples with those based on 24-hour urine measurements (68, 69).

Because of the increased risk of noncompliance in taking the pills and the increased costs in the studies, the World Health Organization (WHO) did not recommend using PABA to assess the completeness of the urine collection in their protocol to measure

population-level sodium intake, because taking the pills may increase the risk of noncompliance or participant drop out (59).

Although there is controversy about urinary sodium being an unbiased estimate of intake, the 24-hour urinary sodium measurement is considered a valid and reliable method for estimating sodium intake, particularly when multiple measurements are taken to account for day-to-day variation in intake.

Potassium

The measurement of 24-hour urinary potassium is generally recognized as a valid and reliable indicator of potassium intake (4). It offers a comprehensive assessment of potassium intake over an entire day, representing an individual's habitual intake. Low urinary potassium has been associated with indicators of poor dietary quality (70). Moreover, lower potassium intakes, measured in at least two 24-hour urine samples, were associated with a higher risk of cardiovascular disease in a pooled analysis of six prospective cohorts (60).

In a strictly controlled study with urinary collections for 30 days ($n = 13$), high correlations between measured intake and 24-hour urinary potassium were reported ($r = 0.89$) (20). High correlations between estimated potassium intake (from diet records) and 24-hour urine samples have also been reported in free-living individuals (4).

Although it is accepted that approximately 77% of dietary potassium is excreted in the urine, there is high within-subject variation (20). After 30 days of urinary collection, participants had an ICC of 0.50 ($n = 13$) (20). In observational studies with repeated measurements, similar variability resulted from four samples within a year in women (ICC 0.48-0.49, $n = 742$) and from two samples within a month in men and women (ICC 0.60-0.65, $n = 2439$) (11). Although the substantial within-person variation has to be considered, two 24-hour samples were sufficient for measuring long-term potassium exposure (11).

The reliability of the 24-hour urinary potassium measurement can be affected by the subject's hydration status. Dehydration can lead to increased urinary potassium excretion. Additionally, participants with higher fiber intake may excrete more potassium in their stools (20), and certain medications, such as diuretics, can also alter urinary potassium excretion (4). Moreover, the method may not be suitable for individuals with kidney disease or other renal impairments.

Despite its limitations, 24-hour urinary potassium has demonstrated comparable performance to urinary nitrogen as a biomarker of intake (20), and, like urinary sodium, urinary potassium has been utilized to evaluate the validity of self-report instruments (71).

4.2 Biomarkers of Food Intake

Dairy products and dairy fat

Dairy products have been associated with different health outcomes, such as risk of hypertension, type 2 diabetes, stroke, and metabolic syndrome (72). Fatty acids present almost exclusively in dairy products in small amounts have been suggested as biomarkers for dairy fat intake. The most established biomarkers of dairy fat intake are the odd chain fatty acids (OCFA): pentadecanoic acid (15:0) and heptadecanoic acid (17:0) (4, 30, 32). Other fatty acid biomarkers that have been described are phytanic acid (4) and trans-palmitoleic acid (trans-16:1n-7) (4), however, there is very limited evidence from intervention studies supporting these biomarkers.

One particular intervention study did find that a higher dairy fat intake (three servings of full-fat dairy products) resulted in a more significant increase in plasma phospholipid trans-16:1n-7 levels compared to OCFA (73). Nevertheless, further intervention studies are needed to establish the suitability of these biomarkers.

Several studies have shown that tissue levels of OCFA are positively associated with dairy intake in both observational and intervention studies (32, 33). In a randomized cross-over trial (n = 124), for example, it was observed that those who consumed three servings of dairy products (milk, yogurt, and cheese) over four weeks experienced a significant increase in serum levels of 15:0 (17% higher) and 17:0 (8% higher) compared to the control phase. However, the levels of trans-16:1n-7 did not show a notable increase during the intervention (74).

In a 12-week intervention trial, the participants (n = 62) consumed diets that were either low in dairy fat (0.3 g/day), rich in low-fat dairy (8.7 g/day of dairy fat), or rich in full-fat dairy (28.5 g/day of dairy fat, equivalent to 3.3 servings/day of full-fat dairy). While plasma phospholipid 17:0 levels did not show any association with dairy fat intake, 15:0 levels were associated with higher dairy fat intake (73).

A higher positive correlation has been observed between dairy fat intake and 15:0 concentrations in adipose tissue (indicating long-term dairy fat intake), compared to the correlation between dairy fat intake and 15:0 in blood fractions (indicating short-term dairy intake) (32, 33). Still, positive correlations have been observed when measuring 15:0 in cholesteryl esters and phospholipids in serum or plasma (32). For example, in a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies, the correlations of dairy fat intake and 15:0 were higher in adipose tissue (r = 0.51), than in total serum (r = 0.31), serum/plasma phospholipids (r = 0.35), serum cholesteryl esters (r = 0.44), and erythrocytes (r = 0.16) (33).

The correlation coefficients between plasma 17:0 and dairy fat and dairy product intake were consistently lower when compared to 15:0 in observational studies (32). In randomized controlled cross-over trials, results indicated that after a diet high in dairy products, the 15:0 concentration was higher compared to 17:0 in plasma cholesteryl esters (75), serum total lipids (76), and plasma total lipids (74). Actually, 17:0 levels were unaffected in two of those studies (75, 76). Current evidence supports that 17:0 concentrations are significantly influenced by endogenous biosynthesis and are not directly related to intake (77, 78).

Information concerning the reliability of plasma fatty acid levels among adults is scarce. The reproducibility of OCFA was good when measured in the Nurses' Health Study (n = 40). The ICC based on two plasma samples over 1-2 years were 0.72 for 15:0 and 0.52 for 17:0 (24). More studies examining the stability of OCFA over time are required.

Other limitations are related to the use of these biomarkers. It is important to note that OCFA may not accurately represent the consumption of low-fat dairy foods, and as a result, they may not reflect overall dairy product intake. OCFA are not completely specific to dairy intake and can also be found in other animal products, such as marine fish (34), thus, it could be an invalid biomarker in populations with high fish consumption.

The metabolism of OCFA is not well understood, and it is unclear how circulating levels of OCFA quantitatively relate to the actual intake of dairy products. The lack of well-controlled validation trials is a limitation of using these biomarkers. The unclear reliability, sensitivity, and specificity may contribute to confounding the interpretation of the results.

Fish

Cold water and marine fish are sources of long-chain n-3 fatty acids, which have been associated with numerous health benefits, including reducing the risk of cardiovascular disease (79, 80), type 2 diabetes (81), and cancer (82). The tissue concentrations of DHA or the sum of DHA with EPA (9) have been proposed as biomarkers of marine fish intake. Although these fatty acids are also found in other aquatic animals (shellfish, lean fish, and some freshwater fish) and terrestrial meat (depending on what they eat), the concentrations are considerably lower in those sources (9).

EPA and DHA have been used to assess compliance with fish intake in interventions and have been strongly correlated with self-reported fish intake in observational studies (9). In an intervention study examining different amounts of fish (90g, 180g, and 270g of salmon), EPA+DHA levels in plasma phospholipids increased in a dose-response manner (35). In another study, when individuals were provided with 200g/day of fish for six weeks, the increase in EPA and DHA levels in erythrocytes was equivalent to that observed when administering 5g/day of fish oil (83). Accordingly, numerous intervention studies have explored the dose-response relationship using fish oils. For instance, EPA+DHA supplementation resulted in the increase of EPA+DHA levels in red blood cells ranging from 44% to 121% across doses between 300mg/day to 1800 mg/day (84).

The reproducibility was measured in the Nurses' Health Study (n = 40). The ICC based on two plasma samples over 1-2 years were 0.68 for EPA and 0.73 for DHA (24). Factors such as the type of fish consumed and the use of supplements may influence the results. Individual variations in metabolism and other factors can further affect the reliability and validity of the biomarkers, so caution should be exercised when interpreting the results. Additionally, the effectiveness of using long-chain n-3 PUFA tissue concentrations as a biomarker for fish intake could be influenced by the consumption of plant-based foods abundant in polyphenols (85). Humans can also synthesize EPA and DHA by converting α -linolenic acid (ALA), but the conversion rate of ALA derived from plant sources is low (86).

The choice of tissue for measuring n-3 fatty acids depends on the duration of consumption under investigation. Shorter-term intake can be reflected in plasma and serum, while red blood cell membranes and adipose tissue are more indicative of long-term (habitual) fish consumption (25, 36). For instance, in serum, levels of EPA

and DHA increased within as little as 4 hours after intake (87). In addition, EPA levels in cholesterol esters and red blood cell membranes were measured after three days of supplementation and were already elevated (37).

In another study, higher levels of EPA in red blood cell membranes were observed even after eight weeks of finishing the supplementation. The concentrations returned to baseline levels when measured 16 weeks after the end of the supplementation period (36). Interestingly, EPA in plasma phospholipids no longer remained higher than baseline two weeks after the supplementation finished, while DHA levels were elevated at two weeks but not at four weeks post-supplementation (36). This supports that red blood cell membranes reflect longer-term intake of omega-3 fatty acids compared to plasma phospholipids. In agreement, when tested weekly over a span of six weeks, red blood cells exhibited lower variability compared to total plasma and total phospholipids (88). It is noteworthy that the incorporation of DHA into cholesteryl esters, red blood cell membranes, and adipose tissue occurs at a slower rate compared to EPA in healthy adults (37).

Adipose tissue has been found to exhibit lower sensitivity to changes in dietary n-3 fatty acids, indicating that the fatty acid content in adipose tissue primarily reflects longer-term fish/fish oil intake. It has been observed that levels of EPA and DHA remained elevated in adipose tissue even six months after discontinuing fish oil intake (37).

Fruits and vegetables

Consuming diets that are abundant in fruits and vegetables has been associated with a decreased likelihood of developing chronic illnesses and reduced mortality (89). The fruits and vegetables food group is complex and has many bioactive compounds in diverse amounts. Several biomarkers can be used to assess the intake of fruits and vegetables, the most established are plasma or serum carotenoids and vitamin C. Although high content variability exists within different fruit and vegetables, results from systematic reviews of controlled studies showed that vitamin C and carotenoids (but not lycopene) are useful biomarkers for general fruit and vegetable intake. However, there was high heterogeneity in the response size between studies and a lack of evidence for a dose-response relationship (47, 90).

- Plasma carotenoids

Carotenoids, primarily present in fruits and vegetables, have been described as biomarkers for assessing the intake of carotenoid-rich foods when measured in plasma (1, 4). Intervention studies have demonstrated that the carotenoids α -carotene, β -carotene, β -cryptoxanthin, and lutein increase in response to increased fruit and vegetable consumption (90).

The concentration of individual carotenoids can exhibit considerable variability after consuming fruits and vegetables, likely influenced by the specific types consumed (90). Although individual carotenoids can provide insights into the consumption of particular types of fruits and vegetables, it is recommended to aggregate multiple carotenoids for a comprehensive assessment of total fruit and vegetable intake. The

sum of carotenoids other than lycopene may be more strongly correlated with total fruit and vegetable than the sum including lycopene (4).

Based on evidence from a systematic review and meta-analysis, few randomised controlled trials have evaluated fasting total plasma carotenoids (90). For example, in a study with men ($n = 64$), carotenoid concentrations were significantly higher in subjects consuming five or eight servings of fruits and vegetables than in those receiving two servings per day for four weeks (38). Similarly, in a cross-over feeding trial in women ($n = 49$), plasma total carotenoids significantly increased in a dose-response manner with three doses of two, five, and ten vegetable servings per day for three weeks (39). Another study found that consuming five servings of fruits and vegetables instead of two per day led to a 29% increase in total carotenoid levels (91).

Compared to plasma vitamin C, the measurement of total plasma carotenoids may have better reproducibility (4). The ICC for total plasma carotenoids, measured twice, showed a value of 0.81 when measured 1-2 years apart (24), 0.70 when measured two to four weeks apart (40), and 0.81 when measured six months apart (41).

Both dietary and nondietary factors can influence the relationship between fruits and vegetable intake and circulating concentrations of carotenoids. Smoking and alcohol intake have been shown to lower carotenoid concentrations (92). Total energy intake, plasma lipid concentrations, BMI, health status, and genetics can also impact carotenoid levels (30, 43, 46, 90). The composition of the overall diet can affect the bioavailability of carotenoids, with higher fat intake increasing their bioavailability (42), while fiber intake may decrease it (43).

Furthermore, the type of food matrix and processing methods, such as homogenization or heat treatment (cooking), can also influence the bioavailability of carotenoids (4, 43). It is also essential to consider the stability of carotenoid biomarkers in biological samples, as they can be affected by factors such as exposure to light during storage and processing (2). Furthermore, it is noteworthy that mixed carotenes and β -carotene are authorised as food additives in the EU (93). For example, fruit juices, soft drinks, breakfast cereals, cocoa and chocolate drinks as well as other dairy products may contain β -carotene additions. Also, many supplements contain β -carotene and contribute to its intake. Despite the sensitivity to fruits and vegetable consumption shown in trials, this limits the specificity of carotenoids as biomarker of intake of these foods.

- Plasma vitamin C

Systematic reviews of randomised controlled trials have indicated that a higher intake of fruits and vegetables leads to increased plasma or serum vitamin C levels (47, 90). For example, in a 4-week randomised intervention study, men and women ($n = 47$) consuming a higher fruit and vegetable (500g) diet had 64% higher fasting vitamin C level than when consuming a lower amount of fruits and vegetables (100g) (44). Another study found that vitamin C levels were higher when consuming five servings of fruits and vegetables daily compared to two servings (45). However, a study involving men ($n = 64$) reported no significant difference in vitamin C concentrations when comparing the consumption of five or eight servings of fruits and vegetables to two servings per day over four weeks (38).

In a systematic review and meta-analysis, no evidence was found to support a dose-response effect when examining the correlation between fruit and vegetable intake

variations and changes in biomarker levels (90). It has been suggested that the response may follow a linear trend only at lower intakes (47). Plasma vitamin C concentrations may reach a peak at 30-60mg/day and no longer demonstrate further increases (90).

Food preparation influences the food content of vitamin C. For instance, cooking vegetables and prolonged storage of fruits and vegetables can lead to declining vitamin C levels (46, 47). Vitamin C, a labile molecule susceptible to oxidation, can also be influenced by factors such as storage conditions and sample processing (46). Factors beyond dietary intake can influence vitamin C levels response, including smoking, inflammation, and BMI(46).

The reproducibility of plasma vitamin C levels has been observed to range from an ICC of 0.29 when measured six months apart (41) to an ICC of 0.84 when measured two-four weeks apart (40). This biomarker is highly responsive to short-term intake, even within three hours (4). Consequently, recent food intake becomes particularly relevant when considering vitamin C levels. Short-term intake may carry less significance in populations with low day-to-day variation in fruit and vegetable intake compared to populations with a higher variation.

Overall, vitamin C and carotenoids exhibit responses to fruit and vegetable intake variations at the group level. However, some of the randomised controlled trials in the latest systematic review were not designed to validate biomarkers and some did not exclude participants using supplements and smokers (90). Additional well-designed, closely supervised randomised controlled trials that encompass various doses and with specific design tailored for biomarker validation are wanted.

Whole-grain wheat and rye

Alkylresorcinols are a group of lipids present almost exclusively in wheat and rye fiber. Numerous studies have investigated plasma alkylresorcinol (AR) concentrations as a promising biomarker for whole-grain wheat and rye intake (94), and evidence is available for a dose-response relation. For instance, in a randomised cross-over trial, participants were given rye bran flakes containing 11, 22, or 44 mg total ARs three times daily for one week. The results demonstrated that total plasma AR levels increased in a dose-dependent manner (95). In two additional intervention studies, plasma AR concentrations were higher among participants with the highest whole-grain intake when compared to those with a medium-dose intake. However, these differences did not reach statistical significance (96, 97).

Fasting plasma AR levels increased after a 6-week period when whole-grain products were provided in comparison to the period when refined-grain products were supplied in a randomised cross-over study (n = 30) (48). Furthermore, the average daily AR intake estimated by weighed food records was positively correlated with plasma AR (r = 0.58) (48). Similar correlations resulted when using mean values of 3 day weighed food records on two occasions, two-three months apart, between plasma AR and whole grain wheat and rye intake (r = 0.53, n = 51) (49). In the same study, the ICC for plasma AR was found to be 0.47 at the two-time points.

A similar level of reproducibility was reported when samples were collected 4-16 weeks apart (ICC = 0.48) (97). Another study, observed a higher reproducibility of fasting plasma AR levels, with an ICC ranging from 0.88 to 0.90 when taking three samples were taken within a 6-week period (n = 17) (50). Additionally, an ICC of 0.68 was observed over a span of 6 to 12 weeks (n = 166) (98).

With a half-life of approximately five hours (99), total plasma AR levels have been proposed as a short-term biomarker of whole grain intake. Still, reproducibility has been demonstrated over two-three months, suggesting it could serve as a medium-term biomarker (50, 100). This could be valid in populations with stable and frequent intake (>2 times per day) but not in populations with less consistent intake (94).

Red blood cell AR levels also respond to whole grain consumption and are positively correlated with plasma AR levels (101). Red blood cell AR levels may serve as a longer-term indicator of whole grain intake compared to plasma AR levels, as they may retain AR during periods of low AR intake (101). Further research is needed to determine the specific time period being reflected by these biomarkers.

Alkylresorcinols are metabolized into the two primary metabolites, which can be also measured in plasma: 3,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (DHBA) and 3-(3,5-dihydroxyphenyl)-1-propanoic acid (DHPPA). Because the half-life of plasma DHPPA (16 hours) is significantly longer than AR (102), plasma DHPPA has been reported to be a good and specific biomarker of whole-grain wheat and rye intake (102, 103). Additionally, studies have demonstrated that the urinary excretion of DHBA and DHPPA exhibits comparable validity to plasma AR concentrations among individuals with high and frequent intake (94). Both DHBA and DHPPA can be quantified in 24-hour urine samples in a manner that reflects a dose-response relationship (95).

The use of AR as a marker for whole-grain wheat and rye products may be limited due to variations in grain levels. Further understanding of AR quantities in cereals and cereal products could improve their use as markers for whole-grain wheat and rye in food products. Conducting studies assessing the reproducibility and reliability of plasma ARs and urinary metabolites in both fasting and non-fasting random samples from diverse populations is important. Additionally, more data is required on AR absorption, metabolism, and clearance in humans.

5. Conclusions

Biomarkers of intake are valuable tools for assessing dietary intake and nutritional status. The selection of biomarkers may depend on the study population, the research question, and the practical considerations of the dietary survey.

In this report, we identified well-established dietary biomarkers suitable for dietary surveys. We have described examples of their validity, reliability, and factors that may influence them. We have also highlighted minimally invasive biological samples collections that impose only a moderate burden on participants: the identified biomarkers can be measured in urine (24-hour samples), blood, and adipose tissue samples.

Certain biomarkers strongly correlate with the intake of specific foods or food components. We identified biomarkers showing validity, reproducibility, and specificity. Those are urinary nitrogen levels as a biomarker of protein consumption, combined urinary sucrose and fructose as a biomarker for sugar intake, and total plasma alkylresorcinol as a biomarker for whole grain consumption. Urinary sodium and potassium exhibit only moderate reproducibility but seem to be valid biomarkers of intake.

The current studies assessing the validity of the biomarkers of fruit and vegetable intake seems to be of low quality, and there is no clear evidence of a dose-response relationship between intake and biomarker. Additionally, when it comes to fatty acids (including essential fatty acids and those acting as biomarkers for dairy and fish intake), available data support the notion that while adipose tissue and blood lipid fraction reflect dietary intake, competition between metabolic pathways can result in changes in fatty acid composition that are not directly linked to diet. Moreover, the polyunsaturated fatty acids biomarkers, such as linoleic acid, and the fish intake biomarkers DHA and EPA, are known to be influenced by genetic variability associated with the metabolism of these fatty acids.

When using these biomarkers in dietary surveys, it is crucial to consider various factors. These include the biomarker's half-life, stability, biological variations, storage requirements of the sample, quality of the analytical method, variations within and between subjects, seasonal and daily timing, and fasting status requirements.

The validity and reliability of biomarkers in reflecting dietary intake are influenced by individual characteristics such as genetic variability, lifestyle, and physiological factors. Therefore, dietary surveys should collect personal characteristics, including age, sex, ethnicity, genetic factors, diseases, hormonal status, supplement use, physical activity level, smoking habits, alcohol intake, and recent dietary intake. Additionally, information regarding the sample should be collected, including storage time between collection and analysis, handling procedures, freeze-thaw cycles, and temperature control. Considering these factors is vital in facilitating the interpretation of biomarker data.

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Supplementary Material

Supplementary Table 1. Overview of preliminary sources of information and which biomarkers were listed

Dietary component measured	Biomarker	Initial sources of information			
		"Nutritional Epidemiology" (Willet, 2013)	"Principles of Nutritional Assessment" (Gibson, 2022)	"Diet, Anthropometry and Physical Activity (DAPA) Measurement Toolkit" (UK)	"Dietary Assessment Primer" (National Cancer Institute, USA)
Protein	Urinary nitrogen	X	X	X	X
Potassium	Urinary potassium	X	X	X	X
Sodium	Urinary sodium	X	X	X	X
Sugar	Urinary sucrose + fructose	X	X	X	X
Fatty acids	Tissue fatty acids	X	X	X	
Dairy fat	Tissue odd chain fatty acids	X	X	X	
Fruits and vegetables	Plasma vitamin C	X	X	X	
Fruits and vegetables	Plasma carotenoids	X	X	X ⁽¹⁾	
Fruits and vegetables	Circulating folate	X	X	X	
Fruits and vegetables	Urine polyphenols	X	X	X	
Whole-grain wheat and rye	Plasma alkylresorcinols	X	X	X	

(1) Lycopene was mentioned as a biomarker of tomato